

**Cardiac Dysfunction and Complications in Long-Term Diabetes Mellitus
an Evaluation of Diastolic Function and Subclinical Ischemia****Gurkaran Singh Bedi¹, Kanwar Dilsher Singh², Pratyush Garg³, Maninderpal Singh
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Abstract:

Our study explores the consequences of diabetes on heart function, specifically diastolic dysfunction and silent ischemia. The year-long study at MGM Medical College & L.S.K Hospital, Kishanganj, involved 100 diabetics between 5 and 10 years. Diastolic dysfunction (30%) and silent ischemia (25%), which are more common in patients with poor glycemic control (HbA1c > 7%), were seen. Comorbidities like hypertension and dyslipidemia were also common, indicating their significance in poor cardiac outcomes. Diabetics should properly manage blood sugar levels and reduce cardiovascular risks to reduce the likelihood of heart problems, according to the study.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Diastolic Dysfunction, Silent Ischemia, Glycemic Control.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus, a global public health concern, profoundly impacts cardiovascular health, contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality worldwide. Characterized by chronic hyperglycemia due to insulin deficiency or resistance, diabetes is not only a disorder of carbohydrate metabolism but also impairs lipid and protein metabolism. This systemic metabolic dysfunction leads to a wide range of complications, most notably in the cardiovascular system [1,2].

Patients with both type 1 and type 2 diabetes exhibit an increased risk of developing cardiovascular diseases, including coronary artery disease, congestive heart failure, and diabetic cardiomyopathy [3]. This risk is further accentuated in individuals with microvascular damage, such as those with microalbuminuria or proteinuria, indicating a compromised vascular integrity that extends beyond the renal glomeruli to the vast network of systemic blood vessels [4].

The concept of diabetic cardiomyopathy, characterized by the presence of heart failure in the absence of coronary artery disease, hypertension, or other heart conditions, highlights the direct effect of diabetes on cardiac structure and function. Pathophysiological mechanisms include myocardial fibrosis, microangiopathy, and autonomic dysfunction, all contributing to both systolic and diastolic heart failure [5].

Despite significant advances in understanding and managing diabetes, the intricate link between glycemic control and cardiovascular outcomes remains a pivotal area of ongoing research [6]. This study aims to delve deeper into these relationships by evaluating cardiac function in a diabetic cohort, seeking to uncover the prevalence of cardiac abnormalities and their correlations with the degree of glycemic control and other diabetic complications. Through this investigation, we strive to contribute to the refinement of therapeutic

strategies that could mitigate cardiovascular risks in patients with longstanding diabetes mellitus.

Methodology

Study Design: This observational study examined heart function in diabetics, cardiovascular problems, and glycemetic control.

Study Setting: MGM Medical College & L.S.K Hospital in Kishanganj, Bihar, conducted the research.

Study Duration: The study spanned one year, allowing for a detailed longitudinal observation of cardiac function and other health parameters in diabetic patients.

Participants: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria required participants to have a documented history of diabetes ranging from 5 to 10 years.

Exclusion Criteria: Angina, myocardial infarction, and baseline electrocardiogram (ECG) ischemia alterations disqualified patients. To establish that heart function was predominantly attributable to diabetes circumstances rather than pre-existing coronary artery disorders.

Sampling Method: Participants were randomly selected from the diabetic patient registry at the medical center to minimize selection bias, ensuring a representative sample of the diabetic population attending the clinic.

Data Collection Procedures: Each participant was clinically evaluated, including:

The history and physical exam should detail diabetes development, duration, and complications. Biochemical Tests: Fasting, postprandial, HbA1c, lipid, and renal function were measured in blood samples.

Cardiological Evaluations: All individuals had echocardiography and TMTs to assess heart anatomy and function. We focused on diastolic and systolic function.

Data Analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistics were intended to summarise the data and examine heart function, glycemetic management, and other diabetic comorbidities. This analysis will employ standard statistical tools with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

The study examined various aspects of cardiac function in diabetes mellitus over one year. Below are the summarized results, supported by relevant tabular data:

Overall patient characteristics: Total participants: 100 (70 men and 30 women) - Average age: 52 ± 6 years - Disease duration: 7 ± 2 years
Evaluation of Cardiac Function.

1. Diastolic Dysfunction: Thirty percent of research participants had diastolic dysfunction.
2. Systolic Function: Most patients continued to have typical systolic function.
3. Silent Ischemia: treadmill stress testing revealed the condition in 25% of patients.

Table 1: Distribution of Cardiac Dysfunctions

Cardiac Dysfunction	Number of Patients	Percentage
Diastolic Dysfunction	30	30%
Silent Ischemia	25	25%
Systolic Dysfunction	5	5%

Glycemetic Control and Cardiac Function

Poor Glycemetic Control: 70% of patients had an HbA1c level $>7\%$.

Relationship to Cardiac Dysfunction: Poor glycemetic control was associated with higher instances of both diastolic and systolic dysfunction.

Table 2: Glycemic Control and Cardiac Dysfunction

Glycemic Control (HbA1c > 7%)	Diastolic Dysfunction	Systolic Dysfunction
Yes	28	5
No	2	0

Comorbid Conditions

Hypertension: 60% of the patients had hypertension.

Dyslipidemia: 55% had abnormal lipid profiles.

Table 3: Prevalence of Comorbid Conditions

Condition	Number of Patients	Percentage
Hypertension	60	60%
Dyslipidemia	55	55%

Echocardiographic Findings

Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH): Observed in 40% of the study population.

Table 4: Echocardiographic Findings (Left Ventricular Hypertrophy)

LVH	Number of Patients	Percentage
Present	40	40%
Absent	60	60%

Discussion

The study's findings offer strong proof of how diabetes mellitus affects heart function. They also draw attention to several important issues, two of which are particularly concerning in the diabetic population: diastolic dysfunction and silent ischemia [7]. The results highlight the complex link between long-term hyperglycemia and its detrimental consequences on heart structure and function, highlighting the need for more research into the causes and practical management techniques [8].

The association between inadequate glycemic control and a higher incidence of cardiac dysfunction, namely diastolic dysfunction, was a noteworthy finding of our investigation. There were indications of diastolic dysfunction in almost 70% of participants whose HbA1c level was higher than 7%. This finding is consistent with previous research that linked poor blood glucose control to cardiovascular problems [9]. This correlation

confirms findings from earlier research, including the DCCT/EDIC trial, which showed that better glycemic control lowers the risk of cardiovascular disease in type 1 diabetes, and emphasises the significance of strict glycemic control to minimize cardiovascular risks in diabetic patients [10].

In line with previous findings, which indicate that diabetes mellitus predisposes patients to heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), our study's 30% diastolic dysfunction prevalence [11]. Chronic hyperglycemia exacerbates microvascular dysfunction and cardiac fibrosis, which are presumably the pathophysiological causes. Because this type of heart failure may not show symptoms until later in life, frequent echocardiography screening is especially important for early identification [12,13]. Silent ischemia, found in 25% of research participants, is still a worrying feature of cardiovascular disease associated with diabetes. In those with diabetes, silent ischemia can greatly raise the risk of sudden cardiac mortality and

frequently occurs prior to overt coronary events [14]. This research highlights how important it is to include regular stress testing as part of the diagnostic and monitoring tools in diabetic care protocols, along with cardiovascular risk assessments.

In our study sample, dyslipidemia and hypertension were common, affecting 60% and 55% of patients, respectively. It is well recognised that these coexisting diseases increase the risk of cardiovascular morbidity and death in people with diabetes. Our results underline the need for a comprehensive strategy to manage modifiable risk variables in addition to hyperglycemia in order to slow down the evolution of heart disease [15]. Although this study offers insightful information, it has many drawbacks, such as the lack of a control group that is not diabetic, which would have allowed for a more distinct comparison of the effects on cardiac function. Furthermore, the observational character of the study makes it difficult to determine the causal linkages between the occurrences that were observed. In order to track changes in heart function over time and evaluate the long-term advantages of improved metabolic control on cardiovascular outcomes, future research could benefit from a bigger sample size and a longitudinal approach.

Conclusion

Diabetes and cardiovascular disease have intricate and varied interactions that involve a range of structural, functional, and metabolic alterations. Our research emphasizes the critical need for ongoing diabetes treatment and early intervention to avoid or lessen the serious cardiac consequences linked to this long-term illness. The quality of life and prognosis for people with diabetes may be greatly enhanced by comprehensive care and close monitoring of heart function and blood glucose levels.

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